

**PURE BENDING OF FIBRE-CORD SYSTEM WITH
DRY FRICTION AT THE INTERFACES**

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ABSTRACT

The paper deals with the internal sliding in a simple cord composite subjected to pure bending. For the case of finite bonding forces associated with friction between the fibres in a cord, it is shown that there is a critical bending curvature at which the onset of slip occurs. The slip starts in the neutral axis of the cross section of the cord and then spreads symmetrically over the cross section with the increase of bending. Some numerical results and their comparison with experiments is given.

Keywords: bending, helical cord, internal slippage.

1. INTRODUCTION

The paper deals with the problem of slip in cords made of helical fibres, and is limited to the analysis of the cord itself without considering its interaction with the matrix. The results presented herein are based on the study of bending and hysteresis of metallic cords done by Huang (1992). The literature on the latter subject can be found in the above cited dissertation.

A model of a cord with six fibres and a core is shown in Fig.1 and global and local coordinate systems are shown in Fig.2. The local coordinate system is given by a trihedron ($\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{b}$) moving along the centerline of the fibre, the unit vectors of the trihedron are as follows: \mathbf{t} is the tangent vector, \mathbf{n} is the vector in the principal normal direction, and \mathbf{b} equals to $\mathbf{t} \times \mathbf{n}$ and is called the binormal vector. In addition, the location of the fibre's centerline can be also determined in polar coordinates (r, φ) .

It was shown (Huang, 1992) that for small bending without slippage the curvatures in the principle normal and binormal directions of the helical fibre, denoted by κ and κ' , and the torsion, denoted by τ , are given by

$$\kappa = -\frac{\sin\alpha_0 \cos^2\alpha_0}{\rho} \cos\varphi \tag{1}$$

Figure 1 A cord model.

$$\kappa' = \frac{\cos^2 \alpha_0}{r} + \frac{\sin^2 \alpha_0}{\rho} \sin \varphi \quad (2)$$

$$\tau = \left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{\sin \varphi}{\rho} \right) \sin \alpha_0 \cos \alpha_0 \quad (3)$$

where α_0 is the helix angle of the fibre in initial configuration, r is the radius of the cylinder on which the centerline is located, ρ is the bending radius of the cord, φ is the polar coordinate of the fibre's center at the cross section of the cord.

In this paper, first some kinematic and stress-strain relationships for the cord and fibres are considered. Then a friction-free cord is discussed in order to introduce the mechanism of slip, and then a case of a finite-friction cord is presented. A numerical example follows.

Figure 2 Coordinate systems for helix.

2. KINEMATICS AND STRAINS

If the bending is such that the dry friction forces between the fibres cannot hold them together any more, a slip occurs. As a result, continuity of deformations in the slipping region would be violated. Also, once internal slippage occurs, a fibre will be bent and twisted around its own neutral axis, instead of around the cord axis when the cord behaves as a solid beam. In this situation, each fibre, because of its dimensions, should be treated as a thin rod and, as a result, the cord is considered as a system of interacting helical thin fibres.

Let us denote the components of the interfibre force acting on the cross section of the fibre by F_t , F_n and F_b and the corresponding components of the moment by M_t , M_n and M_b . The components of the distributed force per unit length of the fibre are p_t , p_n and p_b and those of the distributed moment are m_t , m_n and m_b . If the tangential strain in the fibre is denoted by ϵ_t , then the axial force of the fibre is represented by

$$F_t = A \epsilon_t \quad (4)$$

where $A = E\pi R^2$. For small deformations, the components of the internal moment acting in the cross section of the fibre are related to τ , κ and κ' by

$$(a) M_t = \frac{B}{1+\nu} (\tau - \tau_0), \quad (b) M_n = B(\kappa - \kappa_0), \quad (c) M_b = B(\kappa' - \kappa'_0). \quad (5)$$

where $B = E\pi R^4/4$, E is the Young's modulus of the fibre material, R is the radius of the cross section of the fibre, and the subscript "0" refers to the initial configuration.

Furthermore, considering the fact that there is no radial shear force in the cord's cross section when it is subjected to the axial loads, the shear force component in the principle normal direction of the fibre, F_n , should be equal to zero. This fact was also noted by Costello (1990). When a cord is under pure and small bending, this shear component of the internal force in the fibre is equal to zero, in both cases a cord behaves as a solid beam or as an assembly of free springs. In addition, since the fibre and core are in cross contact, the component of the distributed friction moment m_n should be equal to zero.

For small deformations of the cord, the length of an infinitesimal element of the helical fibre can be approximated by

$$ds \approx ds_0 = \frac{r d\varphi}{\cos\alpha_0} \quad (6)$$

Note that F_t , M_t , M_n and M_b , can be expressed by Eqs.4 and 5 as functions of ϵ_t , τ , κ and κ' . Then substitution of the above relationships into the six equations of equilibrium (Love, 1944) gives the following

$$A \frac{d\epsilon_t}{ds_0} + P_t = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\kappa'_0 F_t - \tau_0 F_b + P_n = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{dF_b}{ds_0} + P_b = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{1}{1+\nu} \frac{d\tau}{ds_0} - \kappa'_0 \kappa + \frac{m_t}{B} = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{d\kappa}{ds_0} - \tau_0 (\kappa' - \kappa'_0) + \frac{\kappa'_0 (\tau - \tau_0)}{1+\nu} - \frac{F_b}{B} = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{d\kappa'}{ds_0} + \tau_0 \kappa + \frac{m_b}{B} = 0 \quad (12)$$

where τ_0 , κ_0 and κ'_0 are the torsion and curvatures in principle normal and binormal direction of the fibre in the initial straight state, and are given by

$$\tau_0 = \frac{\sin 2\alpha_0}{2r}, \quad \kappa_0 = 0, \quad \kappa'_0 = \frac{\cos^2 \alpha_0}{r} \quad (13)$$

It is assumed that each outer fibre remains in contact with the core, so that the centerline of the fibre is always on the cylindrical surface with the radius $r=R_c+R$. From this observation, the expression for the binormal curvature, κ' , may be shown to be the same as Eq.2 which is valid for any curve on the torus. In fact, comparison of Eq.2 for the helix on a torus to that for a free spring (Huang, 1992) shows that the expressions for the binormal curvature κ' in these two cases are very close for the helix angle α_0 up to 90° . Therefore, it is reasonable to approximate in Eq.2 the binormal curvature κ' for a helical fibre in the cord for any friction conditions.

3. SLIPPING MECHANISM

In order to understand the mechanism of the interfibre slippage in a bent cord with dry friction, it is helpful to examine the deformations of the fibre in a friction-free cord. From the condition of no-friction, the following external forces and moments on the helical fibre vanish

$$P_t = P_b = m_t = m_n = m_b = 0 \quad (14)$$

Then from Eqs.2, 12 and 13, the curvature in the principle normal direction is found to be

$$\kappa = -\frac{\sin\alpha_0}{\rho} \cos\varphi \quad (15)$$

When the latter is substituted into Eq.10, the following is obtained

$$\frac{d\tau}{ds_0} = \frac{1+\nu}{r\rho} \sin\alpha_0 \cos\varphi \quad (16)$$

Integration of this equation, subject to the boundary condition that $\tau=\tau_0$ at $\varphi=0$ (in the neutral axis of the cross section), leads to

$$\tau = \frac{\sin 2\alpha_0}{2r} - \frac{(1+\nu)\sin 2\alpha_0}{2\rho} \sin \varphi \quad (17)$$

Finally, when these expressions for κ' , κ and τ from Eqs.2, 15 and 17 are substituted into Eq.11, it is found that

$$F_b = 0 \quad (18)$$

It is of interest to compare these results to those for the free spiral spring (Huang, 1992). As could be expected, they have similar forms and, in the case of $\nu \cos^2 \alpha_0 \ll 2$, give identical results.

From Eqs.7 and 14 it follows that the tangential force component F_t should be constant, because its derivative with respect to the fibre length is equal to zero. From the analogy between the fibres in a friction-free cord under pure bending and the free spiral spring, it is found that

$$F_t = 0 \quad (19)$$

Now let us consider the possible modes of slipping in a friction-free cord. Slip is a discontinuity of displacements between the two surfaces in contact. According to the geometry of a developed helix shown in Fig.3, it is easy to obtain the following relationship between the tangential strain, ϵ_t , and the strain along the cord axis, ϵ_c , in the helical fibre

$$\epsilon_c = (1 + \epsilon_t) \frac{\sin \alpha}{\sin \alpha_0} - 1 \quad (20)$$

Considering that the change of the helix angle before and after the bending is small, the above can be linearized as follows

$$\epsilon_c = \epsilon_t + \frac{\Delta \alpha}{\tan \alpha_0} \quad (21)$$

where $\Delta \alpha = \alpha - \alpha_0$. It follows from Eq.19 that in a friction-free cord ϵ_t will be zero as well. Using Eq.15 and the boundary condition that $\alpha = \alpha_0$ at $\varphi = 0$, $\Delta \alpha$ can be found to be

$$\Delta \alpha = \int_0^\varphi -\kappa \frac{r d\varphi}{\cos \alpha_0} = \frac{r \tan \alpha_0}{\rho} \sin \varphi \quad (22)$$

Then the strain ϵ_c in Eq.21 for the fibre in a friction-free cord equals to

$$\epsilon_c = \frac{r}{\rho} \sin \varphi \quad (23)$$

which is exactly the same as when a cord is considered as a solid beam. It suggests that there is no slipping tendency between the fibre and the core along the direction of cord axis.

On the other hand, when the cord is uniformly bent, the fibre at the very top and bottom of the cross section of the cord will not move. However, the fibres between these points could move. Fig.3 can help to understand how the fibre at the upper part of the cord moves. Because in the case of no-friction there is no internal force in the helical fibre, the length of the fibre would not change

Figure 3 Displacement of the fibre's centerline.

Figure 4 Displacement of fibre's centerline on the cylindrical surface.

($OP_0=OP'$); therefore, in order to incorporate the bending of the cord, the fibre has to slip on the core's surface thereby increasing the helix angle (line OP' moves to OP''). As a result, the trace of the centerline of the fibre would be like that schematically shown in Fig.4. In addition, the twisting and bending deformations of the helical fibres are also the source of slippage. It is known that a twisting deformation is always associated with the bending in a helical fibre; in contrast, there is no twisting deformation in the core whose initial shape is a straight rod. Thus slipping tendency due to the twisting of the fibre always exists in a deformed cord.

4. CRITICAL BENDING CURVATURE AND SLIPPING BOUNDARY

4.1 Bending without slippage

For some level of bending when slippage does not take place, the helical fibre's centerline is simply a helix embedded on a torus. Consequently, the three geometrical parameters, κ , κ' and τ , can be described by Eqs.1, 2 and 3, respectively.

Recalling Eq.21, ϵ_t can be expressed as a function of ϵ_c and $\Delta\alpha$. The axial strain along the cord axis, ϵ_c is given by the simple beam theory

$$\epsilon_c = \frac{r}{\rho} \sin\phi \quad (24)$$

which is the same as Eq.23 for the fibre in a friction-free cord. Note that $\Delta\alpha$ can be found by integrating equation $d\alpha/ds=-\kappa$ (Eq.1) subject to the boundary condition $\alpha=\alpha_0$ at $\phi=0$. The result is

$$\Delta\alpha = \int_0^\phi -\kappa \frac{r d\phi}{\cos\alpha_0} = \frac{r}{2\rho} \sin 2\alpha_0 \sin\phi \quad (25)$$

Substitution of the above two formulas into Eq.21 yields

$$\epsilon_t = \frac{r}{\rho} \sin^2\alpha_0 \sin\phi \quad (26)$$

Then, after substituting ϵ_t together with τ , κ and κ' into the equilibrium equations, Eqs.7-12, the following results for the external distributed forces and moments are found

$$p_t = -\frac{A d\epsilon_t}{ds} = -\frac{A \sin^2\alpha_0 \cos\alpha_0}{\rho} \cos\phi \quad (27)$$

$$p_n = \frac{\sin^2 2\alpha_0}{4r^2\rho} \left[\frac{B(\sin^2\alpha_0 - v\cos 2\alpha_0)}{1+v} - Ar^2 \right] \sin\phi \quad (28)$$

$$p_b = \frac{B \sin\alpha_0 \cos^2\alpha_0}{(1+v)r^2\rho} (\sin^2\alpha_0 - v\cos 2\alpha_0) \cos\phi \quad (29)$$

$$m_t = \frac{B \sin\alpha_0 \cos^2\alpha_0}{r\rho(1+v)} (\sin^2\alpha_0 - v\cos^2\alpha_0) \cos\phi \quad (30)$$

$$m_b = -\frac{B \sin^4\alpha_0 \cos\alpha_0}{r\rho} \cos\phi \quad (31)$$

4.2 Criterion of slippage

Since the fibre is treated as a thin rod, the slippage is defined as the relative displacement of the fibre's cross section with respect to its neighbouring fibres and the core. Such a displacement

becomes possible if on a surface of the fibre, the traction force from all the external loads exceeds the resultant of the interfibre friction forces. From Fig.5 we can present the condition causing an interfibre slip by

$$q_f^2 \leq (p_t - \frac{m_b}{R})^2 + (p_b + \frac{m_t}{R})^2 \quad (32)$$

where q_f is the resultant distributed friction force.

4.3 Critical bending radius and slipping boundary

From Eqs.27, 29-31, we can see that all the friction force components are in inverse proportion to the bending radius and in direct proportion to $\cos\varphi$. Therefore, for a given bending radius of the cord, ρ , the resultant friction force will achieve its maximum at $\varphi=0$. This result shows that the onset of slip takes place at the neutral plane of the bending cord. After taking the equal sign in Eq.32, we can obtain the critical bending radius associated with the onset of slip

$$\rho_c = \frac{1}{q_f} \sqrt{(p_t - \frac{m_b}{R})^2 + (p_b + \frac{m_t}{R})^2} \quad (33)$$

When the results in Eqs.27, 29-31 are substituted in Eq.33, it is found

$$\rho_c = \frac{B \sin 2\alpha_0}{2r q_f} \sqrt{\sin^2 \alpha_0 (\frac{rA}{B} - \frac{\sin^2 \alpha_0}{R})^2 + \cos^2 \alpha_0 (\frac{\sin^2 \alpha_0 - \nu \cos^2 \alpha_0}{R} + \frac{\sin^2 \alpha_0 - \nu \cos 2\alpha_0}{r})^2} \quad (34)$$

As the bending increases, the slip spreads symmetrically from the neutral plane towards the top and bottom of the cross section of the cord. The slipping boundary can be determined from the consideration of equilibrium and compatibility of the internal loads (forces and moments) at the interface of the slipping and non-slipping regions. Obviously, from the concept of dry friction, the distributed friction forces and moments acting on the fibre in the slipping region will be constant. In the following we will identify the forces and moments acting in the fibre's cross section by adding a bar over the notation.

Taking into account the symmetry of the cord structure, only the first quarter of the cross section of the cord, that is $\varphi \in [0, \pi/2]$, is necessary to analyze. Let us consider, for example, the tangential component of the internal force. Inside the slipping region, the corresponding distributed friction force p_t is found by taking $\rho = \rho_c$ and $\cos\varphi = 1$ in Eq.27. The result is

$$\bar{F}_t = \int_0^{\varphi_s} -\bar{p}_t \frac{r d\varphi}{\cos \alpha_0} = \frac{A r \sin^2 \alpha_0}{\rho_c} \varphi \quad (35)$$

At the slipping boundary, which is characterized by the polar angle φ_s on the cross section, the force \bar{F}_t should be equal to that of the fibre in the non-slipping region given by Eq.27. Then it follows that

$$\frac{\varphi_s}{\rho_c} = \frac{\sin \varphi_s}{\rho} \quad (36)$$

Similar relationship can also be found from the equilibrium conditions for other components of internal forces and moments.

Figure 5 External loads acting on the fibre. (a) force and moment components; (b) equivalent traction forces.

5. BENDING OF CORD WITH FINITE FRICTION

For the case of a cord with finite friction, there is always some critical bending curvature, $1/\rho_c$, above which slip occurs and thus the continuity conditions for displacements on the surfaces in contact are violated. In order to find the deformations of the fibre in a slipping state, Eqs.27,29-31 should be solved together with equations of equilibrium Eqs.7-12. Due to space limitations, only the results for the curvature κ and torsion τ (note that $\kappa'=\kappa$) are presented here (see details in (Huang, 1992))

$$\bar{\kappa} = \frac{\sin^3 \alpha_0}{\rho_c} - \frac{\sin \alpha_0}{\rho} \cos \varphi \quad (37)$$

$$\bar{\tau} = \tau_0 - \frac{1+\nu}{2\rho} [(1+\nu) \sin \varphi - \nu \frac{\rho}{\rho_c} \varphi] \quad (38)$$

Now let us check the two bounds of the theoretical model of the cord. First, consider the case when the interfibre friction is absent. In this extreme case, as Eq.34 shows, the critical bending radius becomes infinite, which means that slip starts immediately when the cord is bent. The corresponding curvatures found from Eqs.37-38

$$\bar{\kappa} = -\frac{\sin \alpha_0}{\rho} \cos \varphi \quad (39)$$

$$\bar{\tau} = \tau_0 - \frac{1+\nu}{2\rho} \sin 2\alpha_0 \sin \varphi \quad (40)$$

are the same as Eqs.15 and 17 for the fibre in a friction-free cord.

Alternatively, if the interfibre friction is infinite, the slipping would never occur. It means that the critical bending curvature is always as large as the given bending radius, *i.e.*, $1/\rho_c = \cos \varphi / \rho$ (see the derivation of Eq.33). Then Eqs.37, 38 are reduced to

$$\bar{\kappa} = -\frac{\sin \alpha_0 \cos^2 \alpha_0}{\rho} \cos \varphi \quad (41)$$

$$\bar{\tau} = \left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{\sin \varphi}{\rho} \right) \frac{\sin 2\alpha_0}{2} \quad (42)$$

which are the same as Eqs.1, 3 for the helix fixed on a torus, a condition equivalent to an absolute friction.

6. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

Experimental results by Yu (1952) are used here to compare theory and experiment. The specification is: $n=6$, $R_c=R=1.524\text{mm}$, $L=1.016\text{m}$, $E_c=E=200\text{GPa}$, $\nu=0.25$. In Fig.6 theoretical prediction of the bending stiffness for two different friction forces is shown. In this case, the bending curvature exceeds a critical value and slip occurs inside the cord leading to reduction in stiffness. The transition, in terms of bending deformations, from the non-slipping to fully slipping state is relatively short (note: the horizontal axis is in logarithmic scale). Fig.7 shows that there is a qualitative agreement between the theory and experiment for the bending stiffness.

Figure 6 Stiffness-Curvature relationships for bending cords.

Figure 7 Comparison of bending stiffness from theory to the experiment by Yu (1952).

7. CONCLUSIONS

A theoretical model of a cord which takes into account the interfibre friction and slippage is developed. It is found that there exists a critical bending curvature causing interfibre slippage. A slip starts at the neutral axis and then spreads symmetrically over the entire cross section of the cord. The interfibre slippage and its effect on the reduction of bending stiffness are investigated. A comparison of the model with the experimental results is very encouraging.

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